

HISTORY OF TRANSLATION AND PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATION AT THE PRESENT TIME

Shoymardonova Nargiza

Boykulova Nigina

3rd year student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

e-mail: shoymardonovanargiza@gmail.com

niginaqosimovna@gmail.com

Scientific supervisors: Subanova D.V., Vallamatova S.S.

Abstract: This article describes the history, periods of development, importance and current problems of translation. It was also discussed in detail about the period when translation was divided into major sectors and its role in the life of the state and society.

Keywords: translator, Jacques Francois Champallon, "Rosettik" inscription, gadgets, STR, admiral and special translation.

TARJIMONLIKNING TARIXI VA HOZIRGI DAVRDA TARJIMONLIKDAGI MUAMMOLAR

Shoymardonova Nargiza Hamdam qizi

Boyqulova Nigina Qosim qizi

Ilmiy rahbarlar: Subanova D.V., Vallamatova S.S.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarjimonlikning tarixi, rivojlanish davrlari, ahamiyati va hozirgi kundagi muammolari haqida bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, tarjimonlikning qaysi davrga kelib yirik tarmoqlarga bo‘linishi hamda davlat va jamiyat hayotida tutgan o‘rni haqida batafsil to‘xtalib o‘tilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: tarjimon, Jak Fransua Shampalyon, “Rozettik” bitiktoshi, gadjetlar, FTI, admiral va maxsus tarjimonlik.

As a result of the historical development of humanity, its appearance, economic activity, and spoken languages have also changed. As a result, it became difficult for them to communicate with each other. In such a situation, a category of people who can speak two or more languages was formed, who can help the people who speak different languages to understand each other. These were the first translators.

A **translator** is a specialist engaged in translation work, i.e. creating a written or spoken equivalent of a written or spoken text in one language (source language) in another language (translation language). The professional holiday of interpreters and translators - *International Translators' Day* is celebrated on September 30 [1]. This day was chosen in honor of the Christian Saint Jerome, the Western European translator of the Bible.

Translators had a high position in the early times as well as today. They served mainly in the palaces of the rulers of the country, in the luxurious castles of the nobles and big merchants. They also taught other foreign languages to the children of the noble population [2].

Especially after the "Great Geographical Discoveries" of the XV-XVII centuries, the demand for translators among the big bourgeois merchants increased. As a result, translators took first place among the highest paid professions at that time. Even they were paid more than the Admiral of the ship.

To be more precise, in the first quarter of the 19th century, in 1822, the field of world translation entered a new era. It was on this date that the Frenchman Jacques Francois Champallon succeeded in reading the Ancient Egyptian writing for the first time [3]. He proved that these are not hieroglyphs, but close to the alphabet, based on the translation of the ancient Greek script from the fragment of the "Rosettik" inscription written on paper in Egypt. After this reality, he showed that translators can establish not only relations between peoples, but also relations between science and culture.

After that, translation activity was divided into 2 major branches. These are:

- General translation;
- Special translation.

By the beginning of the 20th century, the demand for translators, especially people who could speak many languages, increased when they were recruited into the special military and security service organizations of the countries. In particular, a point was made that in order to be a special agent of the United States of America (USA), he should be able to speak at least 7 languages.

By the second half of the 20th century, as a result of the scientific and technical revolution (FTI), technology began to have an impact on translation. Now, technology has begun to take the place of translators who require high salaries. Even today, this momentum continues with pictures. According to the scientists of the developed countries of the West, by 2050, people will not need to learn foreign languages, they will be replaced by small gadgets. But taking into account the fact that these are still scientific predictions, we will present a number of problems that need to be solved in the organization of translation activities in Uzbekistan.

First of all, there are not enough jobs for translators in state budget bodies. That is, the translator has a hard time finding a guaranteed job in a specific state organization.

Secondly, translators should be trained based on general translation. In this case, the translator knows a certain language well. But if it is necessary to translate a source related to any field of science, he can only translate what he understands. As a result, his translation becomes shallow. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the training of translators in a specific field. For example, if a translator needs to be an accomplished translator in the field of physics, he must know physics very well.

Thirdly, most translation students in Uzbekistan study in English. While this is positive on the one hand, that is, more than 80% of the world's information exchange takes place, the negative side is that they translate in a language that a large part of society is trying to learn.

Fourth, most translators work as translators in science and other socio-economic fields, serving as mediators of communication between two or more people. This is certainly influenced by the lack of grand funds allocated to the field of translation.

If the above problems are solved systematically, it is possible to bring translation and interpreting activities to a new level. Otherwise, the demand for this field and profession may drop sharply in the period of continuous development of current technology.

References

1. Государственность России: Словарь-справочник. Кн. 5: Должности, чины, звания, титулы и церковные сани России. Конес XV века — феврал 1917 года. Ч. III: М — Я / Сост. Сабенникова И. В., Химица Н. И. — М.: „Наука“, 2005. — 512 с. — С. 143, 194.
2. Boardman, John, et al. eds. The Oxford History of Greece and the Hellenistic World (2nd ed. 2002) 520 pp
3. Anderson, M.S. The Ascendancy of Europe: 1815-1914 (3rd ed. 2003)